

A Data-Driven Framework for Next-Day Traffic Forecasting at Small Airports with Multi-Scale Machine Learning

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Abstract—With the rapid growth in air traffic demand, managing air traffic efficiently has become increasingly challenging, especially for smaller general aviation (GA) airports. Accurate air traffic prediction plays a crucial role in optimizing resource allocation and reducing delays. While existing research predominantly focuses on large airports, GA airports remain understudied despite their unique challenges, such as flexible flight schedules and heightened sensitivity to extreme weather conditions, which complicate forecasting efforts. To address these gaps, this study leverages air traffic data from the Grand Forks International Airport (KGFK), collected via a previously developed Automatic Dependent Surveillance-Broadcast (ADS-B) data collection platform. Weather data from Aviation Routine Weather Report (METAR) reports are integrated with machine learning models to perform time series forecasting of air traffic volume. A Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (SARIMA) model, trained solely on historical air traffic data, serves as the baseline for performance evaluation. Additionally, an eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) model and two Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)-based deep learning models are trained using integrated weather and historical air traffic data to investigate the optimal combination of model structures and weather data resolutions. Results indicate that the multi-scale LSTM-based model outperforms the other models, demonstrating superior fidelity in capturing air traffic seasonality, even with a small dataset comprising 14 days of traffic volume history. Furthermore, while deep learning models exhibit higher predictive performance, the XGBoost model with multi-scale input offers a computationally efficient alternative for small datasets.

Keywords—ADS-B; LSTM; Deep learning; XGBoost; Time Series Forecasting; Air Traffic Management

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I. INTRODUCTION

Air traffic management (ATM) is one of the core functions of airports, playing a vital role in maintaining operational efficiency and safety. To ensure the smooth scheduling of arriving and departing flights, governing and research agencies have developed various management tools [1]. Effective air traffic management requires not only the assignment of available runway environments for flights in the queue but also the allocation of ground support resources, such as fueling facilities, towing vehicles, and ground personnel, for scheduled flights operating at the airport. Consequently, accurate estimates of numbers and timings of upcoming flights are crucial for airport management to prepare and allocate these resources efficiently. This necessity has brought air traffic flow forecasting into focus within the aviation research community.

The development of air traffic estimation has a long history. Early empirical models for forecasting were designed for annual scales and tailored exclusively for towered airports [2]. With the dramatic advancements in computational resources, statistical models such as regression and time series models began to gain prominence. Similar to urban traffic flow, air traffic—especially at regional airports hosting commercial airlines—often exhibits seasonal patterns. As a result, autoregressive (AR) time series models have become a popular choice for air traffic forecasting tasks. These models predict future values by expressing them as a linear combination of historical values and an error term [3].

While AR models perform well on data with strong recursive patterns and clear upward or downward trends, their univariate nature inhibits their applicability to more complex scenarios. Consequently, researchers increasingly adopt sophisticated ensemble learning methods and artificial

intelligence models for modern time series tasks. For example, the eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) model, which integrates a series of complementary weak estimators, and the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network, which excels at capturing relationships across varying time spans, are widely used in traffic volume prediction for large airports [4] [5] [6].

Compared to larger commercial service airports that are often well equipped with aviation data collection systems, air traffic predictions at smaller GA airports present greater challenges for several reasons. First, due to the sensitivity to crosswinds of smaller aircraft using these airports, as well as the fact that many of these airports lack precision instrument landing systems, GA airports have a lower tolerance for extreme weather conditions. Second, the higher scheduling flexibility, or in fact, lack of formal flight schedules for GA operations at small airports increases the uncertainty in the number of flights on a given day. Third, a significant portion of GA airports are non-towered and lack effective data collection systems for recording historical air traffic data, further complicating the prediction process.

To address the challenges in air traffic prediction at small airports, this study leverages locally collected Automatic Dependent Surveillance-Broadcast (ADS-B) data collected from Grand Forks International Airport (KGFK), an airport located in North Dakota that is well known for having large volumes of GA flights, most operating as training flights out of the University of North Dakota flight education program. Individual daily flights, gathered through a previously proposed data collection apparatus, are aggregated into daily flight counts, serving as the objective variable—air traffic volume—in this study. The dataset is further enriched with Meteorological Aerodrome Report (METAR) weather data at two temporal resolutions. Using this comprehensive dataset, a Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (SARIMA) model, an XGBoost model, and two LSTM-based deep learning models are trained to predict next-day air traffic volume. The real-world ADS-B data are employed to validate the models' performance and evaluate their scalability and generalization capabilities. This study seeks to identify the most effective combination of model structures and data configurations for accurately estimating air traffic at GA airports, while also advancing the practical applications of ADS-B data.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II provides a review of the literature on time series forecasting in modern air traffic volume studies. In Section III, we describe the data collection platform, the preprocessing steps, the mechanisms and structures of the models employed in this study. Model results, including performance comparisons and the models' predictions on air traffic volume, are presented in Section IV. Finally, Section V discusses the insights gained from this experiment and outlines future directions for improving model performance.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

With advancements in technology, the field of ATM has undergone a significant transformation. Early air traffic control methods were quickly replaced by radar systems that

leveraged signal reflections in the latter half of the twentieth century. This transition, driven by what is now known as the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA), significantly enhanced the safety and efficiency of air travel through the adoption of data-driven ATM [7].

A critical aspect of ATM is air traffic forecasting, as accurate predictions can reduce delays and optimize resource allocation. Studies show that a 10% improvement in prediction accuracy can lead to a 4% increase in revenue [8] [9]. Lin et al. highlighted temporal-spatial data as key inputs for short-term air traffic flow estimation [10]. Similarly, Du et al. incorporated temporal-spatial data to predict air traffic flows at 30 busiest airports in China, achieving higher fidelity compared to previous benchmarks [11].

Given the temporal nature of variables used in air traffic forecasting tasks, time series models are frequently employed for these projects. AR models, widely used across multiple disciplines, are particularly effective when historical data for dependent variables is available [12] [13]. However, the univariate nature of these models has limited their performance. Advanced models, such as XGBoost and deep learning frameworks are now more commonly applied in the transportation domain [14] [15] [11]. Among these, Wang et al. proposed a Multi-Scale Sliding Window LSTM Framework (MSSW-LSTM) for time series coordinate prediction. This approach outperformed other models using the same training dataset [16].

Beyond temporal-spatial data, weather information has also become a significant focus for researchers. Reitmann et al. integrated weather data into their study and quantified its impact on air traffic operations at London Gatwick Airport (EGKK) using deep learning approaches [17]. Similarly, Nilim et al. optimized the gate-to-gate ATM system with a trajectory-based air traffic management (TB-ATM) model that accounted for weather uncertainty [18].

The widespread adoption of ADS-B technology in recent years has further accelerated the evolution of data-driven ATM, positioning it as a core component of future air traffic management systems. Numerous studies explored the properties and applications of ADS-B data to aid airport managers, data providers, enthusiasts, and researchers [19] [20] [21]. The extensive deployment of ADS-B transponders has also spurred the development of advanced data collection platforms. Researchers and commercial data providers established multiple ADS-B data-gathering networks [22] [23] [24]. These platforms enable real-time visualization of flights within a study area, provide detailed kinematic information, and generate comprehensive traffic flow statistics [25] [26]. Since these statistics can be disaggregated to any resolution, they offer significant potential for conducting air traffic flow studies.

Current research on air traffic forecasting primarily focuses on short-term traffic flows, typically measured in hourly units, and often centers on enroute traffic and traffic in and out of commercial service airports. However, GA airports, which are more sensitive to rapid changes in traffic flow remain understudied. This study aims to address this gap by utilizing a sliding window approach for multi-scale data generation.

Figure 1: An Example of ADS-B Data Collection Units

The generated data will be employed for next-day air traffic prediction.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection & Preprocessing

Tasked by FAA, our team proposed an ADS-B data collection scheme. Due to the FAA’s mandate [27], ADS-B transponders are now widely installed on aircraft operating in U.S. airspace, enabling researchers to study the flight positions and kinematics of individual flights. In this study, data collection units consisting of Raspberry Pi processors, data storage, communication modules, and data filtering systems were installed at GA airports to gather flight trajectory data and extract capacity parameters. An illustration of the data collection unit is shown in Fig. 1.

The raw ADS-B messages collected by these units are transmitted in real time to a data analytics system hosted on Amazon Web Services (AWS). These messages are decoded and processed to reconstruct complete flight trajectories, which are subsequently stored in a PostgreSQL database. This system enables the determination of traffic flow at any GA airport equipped with our infrastructure by aggregating daily flight operations at the given airport. In this study, we chose the KGFK airport and time period August 21, 2021 to January 11, 2025 due to the long time span and the abundance of historical flight records in our database. However, during this period, certain days with no recorded traffic, caused by interruptions in our equipment, were excluded to prevent deep learning models from learning irrelevant patterns associated with such human-induced data gaps.

Beyond historical air traffic data, the significant influence of weather on small airports, compared to regional airports, necessitates the integration of METAR data, which provides detailed surface weather information. To prepare the METAR data for integration with air traffic data, it is preprocessed and narrowed down to four relevant variables: wind direction, wind speed, visibility, and snow depth. Considering that all four runways of KGFK airport are oriented either north-south or east-west, as shown in Fig. 2, the hourly wind

Figure 2: Runway Layout of KGFK

direction and wind speed variables are transformed into north-heading and east-heading wind components for better alignment with runway operations. Snow depth, typically reported every six hours during snowy conditions, is interpolated for intermediate time points to ensure data continuity. Although METAR reports are scheduled hourly, additional reports are issued in response to significant weather changes, resulting in inconsistent reporting frequencies [29]. To handle these irregularities, the average value for each weather variable is calculated for every hour of the study period. Missing hourly data are then interpolated to create a complete dataset. For single-scale model training, the daily averages of each variable are also computed, as detailed in the following sections.

To make the training of XGBoost and deep learning models more efficient, we preserve the time-sequential structure of the weather information using a sliding window approach. The data are first processed into a single-scale format, where all independent variables are aligned with the same time scale (e.g., minute, hour, or day) and time span. This ensures that the input tensors for deep learning models have a consistent rectangular shape. The choice of sliding window width is particularly important, as it determines how many days of air traffic data will lack complete historical information and need to be excluded at the beginning of the time sequence. With fewer than 1,300 usable days in the dataset and considering the large number of parameters in the LSTM layers, we select a 14-day sliding window to strike a balance between model complexity and data availability.

For each valid date with complete historical data, let the air traffic volume on that date (the dependent variable) be Y_n . The traffic volume for the preceding 14 days, ranging from Y_{n-14} to Y_{n-1} , is extracted as the traffic volume feature for this iteration. Similarly, let X denote the weather variable

matrix. The weather data for the same 14-day period, from X_{n-14} to X_{n-1} , is extracted as the weather feature for this iteration. These traffic volume and weather variables are then combined to form the final single-scale tensor with a shape of $[998, 14, 4]$, where 998 represents the total number of valid days, 14 is the sliding window width, also referred to as the time steps, and 4 is the number of variables. A graphical illustration of this process is shown in Fig. 3a. Finally, to incorporate date information, the target dates (n) are transformed into weekday and month representations.

Similar to the single-scale sliding window, a 14-day air traffic volume window is also selected for generating multi-scale data. However, for weather data, a 24-hour window is used to construct the weather tensor. Specifically, the hourly weather data from $X_{n-1,0}$ to $X_{n-1,23}$ of the day $n-1$ are aggregated to form a weather tensor with a shape of $[1, 24, 4]$ for any day n , as illustrated in Fig. 3b. Despite the different window widths, the first dimension (i.e., the sample size) of both the final weather tensor and the air traffic volume tensor equals the total number of valid dates. It is worth noting that tensors are generated exclusively for the LSTM-based models, while the multi-scale time steps are unfolded into individual variables in a *Pandas* dataframe format when training the XGBoost model, as the latter lacks mechanisms for directly handling time steps. Both tensors and dataframes are split into training sets (80%), validation sets (10%), and test sets (10%). All model trainings are conducted on the training sets, and performances are evaluated on the validation sets. For each model category and structure, the one with the best performance on the validation sets is selected for evaluation on the test sets.

The final model performances are assessed using the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), which are defined as in (1) and (2), respectively:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i|, \quad (1)$$

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}, \quad (2)$$

where n is the total number of data points, y_i represents the true value for the i -th data point, \hat{y}_i is the predicted value for the i -th data point. The model selection during the grid search is also guided by these metrics. The performance of the tuned models will be presented in the following sections.

B. Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average

SARIMA, a variant of the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model, is designed to handle time series forecasting tasks with pronounced seasonal patterns. Similar to ARIMA, it combines several steps within its internal estimation process: autoregression (AR), differencing (I), and moving average (MA). Additionally, SARIMA introduces a seasonal differencing component $(1 - B^s)^D$, where B^s denotes the backshift operator with a seasonality of s . This extension allows SARIMA to effectively model both

Figure 3: Single-Scale VS Multi-Scale Sliding Window

non-seasonal and seasonal patterns in time series data. The SARIMA model can be formally expressed as in (3) [29]:

$$\phi_p(B)\Phi_P(B^s)(1-B)^d(1-B^s)^D Y_t = \theta_q(B)\Theta_Q(B^s)\varepsilon_t, \quad (3)$$

In this equation, $\phi_p(B)$ and $\Phi_P(B^s)$ represent the non-seasonal and seasonal autoregressive components, respectively. $(1-B)^d$ corresponds to the non-seasonal differencing operation, while $(1-B^s)^D$ accounts for seasonal differencing. $\theta_q(B)$ and $\Theta_Q(B^s)$ denote the non-seasonal and seasonal moving average components, respectively. Finally, ε_t represents the error term at time t .

In this research, a Dickey-Fuller test is performed on the air traffic volume over time, confirming the stationarity of the data at the 0.05 significance level. Consequently, the differencing procedures (d and D) are not required. The remaining parameters of the SARIMA model are determined using the Autocorrelation Function (ACF) plot, which measures the correlation of a data point with previous points in the time series at various lags, and the Partial Autocorrelation Function (PACF) plot, which isolates the direct correlation of a data point with previous points by removing the influence of intermediate lags. Through a grid search algorithm, the non-seasonal and seasonal orders of the AR and MA components are optimized and set to $(1, 1, 4, 7)$, with a weekly seasonality added into the model.

C. XGBoost

Gradient Boosted Decision Tree models (GBDT) are a class of ensemble learning algorithms composed of a series of decision trees. Each tree is trained to minimize the residual error of the previous tree, thereby contributing to a robust overall estimation. Building on the traditional GBDT framework, XGBoost extends the idea of combining weak learners into a strong learner in a recursive manner. However, unlike GBDT, which uses only the residuals (first-order derivatives),

XGBoost employs a second-order Taylor expansion of the loss function to dynamically adjust learning rates, optimizing overall performance [30].

In addition to this enhancement, XGBoost introduces several advantages over GBDT, including the ability to handle missing values directly, the incorporation of regularization terms to reduce overfitting, and support for parallel computation during node splitting. These improvements significantly boost both the efficiency and performance of the model, particularly when dealing with datasets with high dimensionality. These features make XGBoost particularly suitable for our task, where multiple time steps of weather and traffic volume data are unfolded into 38 separate variables.

The low bias of XGBoost models comes at the cost of high variance. To ensure the model's ability to generalize effectively in future predictions, multiple regularization methods, in addition to those already incorporated into the objective function, are applied during training. The number of trees, the depth of the trees, and the learning rate are carefully controlled to prevent overfitting of individual trees.

Additionally, randomness is introduced into the column selection process during node splitting through the `colsample_bytree` parameter in the *sklearn* package. The optimal combination of the above-mentioned hyperparameters is identified using a grid search combined with expanding window cross-validation. The best parameters are as follows:

- `colsample_bytree`: 0.8
- `learning_rate`: 0.075
- `max_depth`: 5
- `n_estimators`: 50

D. LSTM-Based Deep Learning Models

Regular deep learning structures are not capable of handling data with time sequence; hence Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) were invented to fill this gap. The recurrent mechanism allows RNNs to remember temporal dependencies and realize sequential processing, and thus RNNs are commonly used in tasks that involve sequential data, such as natural language processing (NLP) and time series modeling. However, the regular RNNs suffer from the vanishing gradient problem when the backpropagation travels through a numbers of time steps; this will impede the learning of long-term dependencies and create short-term bias. LSTM is thus developed to solve these problems with a unique gate mechanism.

As shown in Fig. 4, an LSTM cell at time step t comprises three gates: the forget gate (F_t), the input gate (I_t), and the output gate (O_t). The forget gate determines the extent to which the input X_t and the hidden state from the previous time step H_{t-1} should be retained and merged into the internal state, using a *sigmoid* activation function. Similarly, the input gate controls how much of the input contributes to updating the internal state. Intuitively, the output gate regulates the information passed to the output at time step t . The calculations for these gates are given in (4), (5), and (6):

Figure 4: LSTM Cell Architecture

$$I_t = \sigma(X_t W_{xi} + H_{t-1} W_{hi} + b_i), \quad (4)$$

$$F_t = \sigma(X_t W_{xf} + H_{t-1} W_{hf} + b_f), \quad (5)$$

$$O_t = \sigma(X_t W_{xo} + H_{t-1} W_{ho} + b_o), \quad (6)$$

where W represents the weights of the gates, and b represents the biases. Beyond the gates, the internal state C_t plays a crucial role in learning long-term dependencies. It serves as a pathway for gradients during backpropagation, bypassing multiple activation functions, which helps mitigate the vanishing gradient problem. The calculation of the internal state is given by (7):

$$C_t = F_t \odot C_{t-1} + I_t \odot \tilde{C}_t, \quad (7)$$

where \odot denotes the elementwise (Hadamard) product, and \tilde{C}_t is the candidate internal state, computed by passing the linear combination of X_t (input) and H_{t-1} (previous hidden state) through a *tanh* activation function.

Finally, the hidden state H_t at this time step is computed using the output gate O_t , as shown in (8):

$$H_t = O_t \odot \tanh(C_t), \quad (8)$$

This mechanism enables LSTM to effectively model both short-term and long-term dependencies in sequential data. For the single-scale tensor, two stacked LSTM layers are employed. Each LSTM layer consists of 16 units, and the output of the second LSTM layer is concatenated with the date variables (i.e., weekday and month). The combined data are then passed through a four-layer multi-layer perceptron (MLP) with 16, 16, 8, and 4 neurons in each layer, respectively. This architecture was empirically identified as the optimal configuration among various structure and parameter combinations.

For the multi-scale tensor, two parallel LSTM layers, each with 16 units, are employed. To reduce the risk of overfitting caused by rapid variations in weather patterns, a dropout rate of 20% is applied to the input of the weather LSTM layer. This dropout mechanism randomly deactivates a fraction of the input features, thereby improving the model's generalization ability. The outputs of the two LSTM layers are concatenated with the date-related information and passed through a four-layer fully connected network, comprising layers with 16, 16, 8, and 4 neurons, respectively.

Figure 5: Architectures of LSTM-Based Models

Both LSTM-based models utilize the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0002 for its ability to adapt dynamically during training. The models are trained for 100 epochs with a batch size of 16 to balance the limited sample size and generalization. The architectures of the LSTM-based models are illustrated in Fig. 5.

IV. RESULTS

The air traffic flow over the chosen period at KGFK is depicted in Fig. 6, with zero-traffic days highlighted in red. As mentioned earlier, these zero-traffic days, along with data points whose sliding windows include these days, are excluded from the analysis. Although this may slightly disrupt

Figure 6: Daily Air Traffic Volume at KGFK

the continuity of the air traffic sequence, the inclusion of date-related variables helps mitigate this issue, as evidenced by the model results.

Fig. 6 reveals significant variance in air traffic within most weeks, with recurring peaks and troughs at approximately weekly intervals. The busy season at KGFK begins in early September, likely driven by the return of student pilots from the University of North Dakota, favorable weather conditions, and agricultural activities. Following November, traffic gradually declines, reaching a low point in early January, potentially due to the holiday season and adverse weather conditions, such as heavy snow and storms.

It is noteworthy that the seasonality of air traffic at this GA airport is less pronounced compared to other GA and some commercial airports, especially when the time unit is aggregated to a day. However, the PACF plot indicates strong but decaying autocorrelations between the current day's air traffic volume and that of 7, 14, 21, and 28 days prior, highlighting a recurring weekly pattern.

The SARIMA model is initially trained as a baseline model, utilizing only historical traffic data as input without accounting for the effects of weather on operations at KGFK. While SARIMA is widely used for sequence estimation in both engineering, to avoid the accumulative bias typically introduced by self-generated predictions and ensure consistency with other models employed in this study, the SARIMA model's internal linear parameters are fixed in testing, and predictions are generated recursively, one step at a time. The results on the test set are illustrated in Fig. 7.

The SARIMA model demonstrates the ability to provide relatively accurate estimates for cycles with a typical 7-day duration. However, this capability can sometimes be detrimental. Without incorporating weather variables, the model continues to predict 7-day peaks, even during early 2025 when the true values approach zero. Beyond this period, when the cycle length (i.e., seasonality) is disrupted by unexpected factors, the model initially follows the original pattern before quickly adjusting based on the traffic volume from the previous day. This adjustment introduces "delays" in the predictions relative to the true values. On the test

Figure 7: SARIMA Predictions on Test Dataset

set, spanning from October 5, 2024, to January 11, 2025, SARIMA achieves a MSE of 197.47. In comparison, the estimation using the mean of the training set results in an MSE of 260.98.

The multi-scale XGBoost’s predictions for the entire dataset are illustrated in Fig. 8. Although the model still demonstrates a delayed reaction to volume changes, incorporating the prior 24 hours of weather data into the training process makes XGBoost more adaptable. This flexibility is particularly evident during the traffic volume trough in January, where the recursive fluctuation pattern is suppressed by the impact of heavy snow. Additionally, XGBoost’s adaptability is further highlighted by the less pronounced seasonality in its predictions compared to SARIMA.

Another notable advantage of XGBoost is its interpretability. Due to its tree-based structure, the reduction in MSE can be used to quantify feature importance, as shown in Fig. 9. The most important variable is the air traffic volume from one day prior, aligning with the parameter configuration of SARIMA. Additionally, the air traffic volume from the same day of the previous week highlights the weekly seasonality in the data. Weather-related variables, such as snow depth and northward wind speed from the previous day, also rank among the most significant predictors. Furthermore, date-related variables, such as the day of the week and month, hold prominent positions in the feature importance ranking, reflecting the

model’s ability to capture yearly patterns effectively.

Figure 9: Variable Importance of XGBoost

In terms of training and estimation speed, the XGBoost model, encompassing 210 grid search parameter combinations, completes training in just 2 minutes and 23 seconds, showcasing the high efficiency of parallel computation. In contrast, SARIMA requires over 3 minutes for each parameter combination during the training phase, with the recursive estimation phase taking a similarly long time. This discrepancy stems from the larger sample size involved in the historical air traffic data and the computationally demanding maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) process utilized by the SARIMA algorithm.

The single-scale LSTM-based model fails to extract meaningful information from the historical daily weather data. Despite multiple attempts to adjust the model structure and fine-tune hyperparameters, the best MAE on the test set remained at 197.36. This result underscores the superiority of the multi-scale data structure, as weather trends can only be effectively captured using hourly data. Moreover, 24 hours of weather data proved sufficient information for this purpose, as experiments incorporating 48 hours of data showed no improvement in test MAE. Due to the model’s inability to effectively utilize weather data, low-traffic days with fewer than 200 flights—caused by extreme weather events in late

Figure 8: XGBoost Predicted and True Air Traffic Volume

(a) Single-Scale LSTM-Based Model Predicted and True Air Traffic Volume

(b) Multi-Scale LSTM-Based Model Predicted and True Air Traffic Volume

Figure 10: Single-Scale LSTM-Based Model VS Multi-Scale LSTM-Based Model

December and early January—were overlooked, leading to suboptimal overall performance.

The predictions generated by the multi-scale LSTM-based model and the single-scale model are presented in Fig. 10a and Fig. 10b, respectively. Both models exhibit certain similarities: the aforementioned estimation “delays” are evident in both cases, and they successfully capture the seasonal patterns, including the troughs observed during winter. However, a notable difference is that the multi-scale model is able to capture a shorter low-volume period in mid-November, which the single-scale model fails to identify.

The advantages of the multi-scale structure are particularly evident in this comparison. The predictions on the training, validation, and testing datasets exhibit a broader dynamic range compared to the single-scale model. This improved spread indicates that the multi-scale model is better in capturing extreme traffic volumes caused by weather conditions.

Examining the performance of the multi-scale XGBoost model, its short-term forecasts align more closely with the true trend. However, due to estimation delays, the significant differences between peaks and troughs contribute to larger biases. The multi-scale XGBoost model achieves an RMSE of 182.66, while the multi-scale LSTM-based model delivers a slightly better MAE of 178.79. Although the improvement

appears marginal, the two models demonstrate complementary strengths. The XGBoost model excels in estimating traffic on low-traffic days within the test dataset, whereas the multi-scale LSTM-based model significantly outperforms in medium-traffic scenarios, particularly on days with air traffic volumes between 200 and 600 flights, with a gap exceeding 30 flights. Both models show comparable performance when estimating traffic on high-traffic days (over 600 flights). A detailed summary of the models’ performances on the overall test set and on days with varying traffic volumes is provided in Table. I. Notably, since the test dataset spans the period from late 2024 to early 2025, it contains a higher proportion (47.96%) of low-traffic days. This distribution narrows the performance gap between the XGBoost model and the multi-scale LSTM-based model.

V. DISCUSSION

Leveraging the ADS-B data collected by a previously proposed data collection platform, this study extracted the daily air traffic volume at KGFK for a multi-year period. By integrating the air traffic dataset with METAR weather data, we generated multi-scale and single-scale time series training datasets using a sliding window approach. These datasets were used to train four models: SARIMA, multi-

TABLE I. Performance Comparison Across Models

Dataset	SARIMA		XGBoost		Single-Scale LSTM		Multi-Scale LSTM	
	MAE	RMSE	MAE	RMSE	MAE	RMSE	MAE	RMSE
Test Dataset	197.47	252.83	182.66	222.29	197.357	230.44	178.79	221.66
Low-Traffic	155.41	213.48	160.09	195.05	192.25	221.72	178.56	212.95
Medium-Traffic	218.01	251.36	152.71	185.43	155.37	192.23	119.61	154.39
High-Traffic	255.37	313.88	252.27	290.54	290.92	316.43	259.27	293.10

scale XGBoost, single-scale LSTM-based model, and multi-scale LSTM-based model. Among these models, the multi-scale models demonstrated superior performance on a test set spanning from October 5, 2024, to January 11, 2025.

The SARIMA model, which uses only historical air traffic volume as input, was employed as a baseline for comparison. In contrast, the single-scale LSTM-based model, which relies on daily average weather data, struggled to effectively capture the impact of weather on air traffic. The multi-scale models, incorporating air traffic and weather data across different time spans and units, excelled in modeling both recurrent traffic patterns and weather effects. The XGBoost model proved effective in predicting traffic volume on low-traffic days, while the LSTM-based models demonstrated greater accuracy in estimating medium-traffic volumes, particularly for days with traffic between 200 and 600 flights. Notably, the multi-scale LSTM model achieved slightly better MAE and RMSE compared to the XGBoost model. However, this gap is expected to widen when testing on datasets from other periods, such as mid-year data.

This study demonstrates that the multi-scale sliding window approach is well-suited for predicting air traffic flow, particularly at GA airports, which are more sensitive to weather changes compared to regional airports. By leveraging the multi-scale datasets, both the XGBoost and LSTM-based models provide valuable predictions that can assist small airports in optimizing resource allocation. Furthermore, the interpretability of the XGBoost model enhances our understanding of air traffic management by shedding light on weather factors influencing traffic patterns. The model could facilitate the work of airport operations coordinators by providing accurate predictions of next-day traffic volume by the end of each day. With this foresight, coordinators can make informed decisions regarding staff scheduling, runway and taxiway usage, and refueling infrastructure. Additionally, the integration of air traffic data expands the potential applications of ADS-B data, offering significant benefits to the research community and advancing the field of air traffic studies.

This study can be further improved in several aspects. The ADS-B data collection platform at KGFK was initially installed in 2021, providing a limited three-year data span. After excluding no-traffic days, the reduced sample size constrained the sliding window width, thereby limiting the performance of models and resulting in suboptimal predictions for extreme values. To overcome this limitation, future work will focus on utilizing longer time sequences—such as datasets spanning over 1500 valid days—and exploring advanced architectures like Transformer and Informer to improve predictive accuracy

and robustness. Since cloud ceiling is a key determinant in whether Visual Flight Rules (VFR) or Instrument Flight Rules (IFR) are applied—and therefore directly impacts air traffic volume—future research will incorporate this variable in the next version of the models.

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